

Penetration Testing using Albanian Websites

¹⁾ Amanda Zeqiri

Department of Applied Mathematics
Faculty of Natural Science, University of Tirana, Albania
Tirana, Albania
amanda.zeqiri@fshn.edu.al

²⁾ Igli Tafa

Department of Information Engineering
FIT, Polytechnic University of Tirana
Tirana, Albania

³⁾ Doris Fejza

FIT, Polytechnic University of Tirana
Tirana, Albania

⁴⁾ Alesia Qirici

FIT, Polytechnic University of Tirana
Tirana, Albania

Abstract— Penetration test is a process used for verifying systems and networks that are not vulnerable to a security risk. Vulnerability could allow hackers attack the software and infrastructure. This article includes all the steps of preparing and performing a pen test by introducing its methodologies, application scenarios and tools using an Albanian website. The reason why we prepared this article is that Albanian web pages are vulnerable to security risks.

The process of performing a pen test is complex. However, it is better for each company to test the security of their software using penetration test.

Keywords: Security Testing, Vulnerability, Penetration Testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, companies are focused on the functionality of their software by implementing new applications that give a better service and convenience for the customers. Evaluating the security state is a required task to detect the risks. To perform this evaluating is necessary the use of security tests. The one we used it is called penetration test, which is one of the known forms of testing the security risk. The simulation penetrates into a system or network to identify vulnerabilities before they can be utilized, by using same techniques as a hacker.

Figure 1

We prepared this article using Albanian web pages because it's noticed that they are vulnerable to security risk. The website we utilized for penetration test is www.akep.al. The process is divided into these activities such as gathering the data of the target system, scanning the target system to discern the available protocols and services, determining the existing applications and exploiting the known vulnerabilities in the systems.

So, this article is organized into several sections including all steps of the test by introducing the followed methodology and the required tools, all obtained results and the conclusions about this article.

II. THE RELATED WORK

Penetration test methodology is separated in six phases. The first one is Information gathering in which we gathered all information based on server such as the correct domain of web server and the numbers of sub-domains that are connected to this domain.

Then took place the next phase scanning and reconnaissance. In this phase we used to know the targets by using passive methods such as network scanning and researching available information. For scanning we used a tool named NMAP (Network MAPPER).

Threat Modeling is the third phase of penetration testing. We did this model to present all the security concerns and their solutions. Continuing on with the fourth step which is vulnerability analysis that we have identified the vulnerabilities. Exploitation is the fifth phase in which we gained the access by gaining access by breaking the security of a system.

In our case for finding the vulnerability in web server we used Nikto.

Finally, the last step we did was Post-Exploitation Reporting in which we detailed the vulnerabilities that we found and provided some information based on the tests we performed about the website.

III. INTRODUCING THE ENVIRONMENT

For the performed penetration test is used Kali Linux 2020.1 version, installed on a Hp Elite Book laptop. Kali Linux is a Debian Linux distribution used to test and audit the security of a system/network. Kali contains tools such as Security research, Penetration Testing and Computer Forensics.

IV. TOOLS

The Kali tools used are: Nikto, TheHarvester, Uniscan, SqlMap and GoLismero. Golismero is known as “Web Knife” and is also an open source framework for security testing focused on web security. Golismero as a security framework which searches for vulnerabilities contains other tools like Wfuzz, DNSEnum, DNS recon, nmap, OpenVas, SQLMap, Shodan and it takes their combined results and displays them as a report. The Golismero project is fully- written in Python language.

Nikto is a web server which scans web servers for malicious files and is an open source project. Nikto has a database of 6700 potentially malicious actors and has more than 1455 outdated server’s versions. Nikto checks websites for malicious index files and tries to understand what web servers are installed. It supports SSL, HTTP, XSS, also scans open ports on a server and all the reports are saved as XML, CS V or HTML.

TheHarvester gathers website’s domain, subdomains, hosts, account’s emails and also checks for open ports by displaying also the real IP of websites. TheHarvester works like this because use PGP key servers and Shodan database engine. Pentesters use this tool in order to gather website’s footprint and use this to understand the organizational unit of a company if needed.

Uniscan is a vulnerability scanner and behaves as an RFI (Remote File Inclusion), LFI (Local File Inclusion), RCE (Remote Command Execution). Uniscan also is an enumeration tool and gathers open ports status and protocol corresponding to target. It’s one of the most advanced tools to scan a website.

SQLMap is an automated SQL Injection tool which exploits remote databases by extracting their tables, columns and names. It’s written in python and is an open source pentest tool. SQLMap searches and exploits SQLi (SQL injection) vulnerabilities and can take over a database server. Also, it can execute remote commands after it can break through the database by utilizing some out of band connection.

V. TESTS AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

A. Nikto

We have used Nikto for scanning the website with SSL and without SSL, using respectively port 443 and port 80. In first case we get the type of ssl, which we can exploit for getting further information subject field we notice the Common Name (CN) which is the name of server protected by SSL. Exploiting this we can access the website where the web is hosted. The server is Apache, while the webserver used for emails is ILoHaMail which is vulnerable against XSS. Through making a

XSS attack to ILoHaMail attackers can access and read their emails. Through /securecontrolpanel we can gain access to admin Panel./cgi-sys/Count.cgi may allow attackers to make fixes end execute code remotely.

```
Nikto v2.1.6
-----
+ Target IP:      192.168.39.62
+ Target Hostname: www.akep.al
+ Target Port:    443
-----
+ SSL Info:      Subject: /CN=akep.fj-technology.com
                  Ciphers: ECDHE-RSA-AES256-GCM-SHA384
                  Issuer: /C=US/O=Let's Encrypt/CN=Let's Encrypt Authority X3
+ Start Time:    2020-02-26 15:40:06 (GMT)
-----
+ Server: Apache
+ The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options header is not present.
+ The X-XSS-Protection header is not defined. This header can hint to the user agent to protect against some forms of XSS
+ Location header 'x-redirect-by' found, with contents: WordPress
+ The site uses SSL and the Strict-Transport-Security HTTP header is not defined.
+ The site uses SSL and Expect-CT header is not present.
+ The X-Content-Type-Options header is not set. This could allow the user agent to render the content of the site in a different fashion to the MIME type
+ Root page / redirects to: https://akep.al/
+ Uncommon header 'link' found, with contents: <https://akep.al/wp-json/>; rel="https://api.w.org/"
+ Cookie PHPSESSID created without the secure flag
+ Cookie PHPSESSID created without the httponly flag
+ Entry '/wp-admin/admin-ajax.php' in robots.txt returned a non-forbidden or redirect HTTP code (400)
+ 'robots.txt' contains 2 entries which should be manually viewed.
+ Hostname 'www.akep.al' does not match certificate's names: akep.fj-technology.com
+ Web Server returns a valid response with junk HTTP methods, this may cause false positives.
+ /webmail/d/blank.html: ILoHaMail 0.8.10 contains an XSS vulnerability. Previous versions contain other non-descript vulnerabilities.
+ /securecontrolpanel/: Web Server Control Panel
+ /webmail/: Web based mail package installed.
+ /cgi-sys/Count.cgi: This may allow attackers to execute arbitrary commands on the server
+ ERROR: Error limit (20) reached for host, giving up. Last error: Total transaction timed out
+ Scan terminated: 10 error(s) and 17 item(s) reported on remote host
+ End Time:      2020-02-26 16:42:46 (GMT) (13760 seconds)
```

Figure 2 Nikto scanning 1.

In second case we get more information about vulnerabilities given that we can analyze incoming requests. Through port 80 we get information about OSVDB’s (The Open Sourced Vulnerability Database). For example attackers can exploit the input validation problem that exists in cpanel, which allows injecting carriage return and line feed characters into the header of server HTTP response.

```
--- Nikto -h www.akep.al
Nikto v2.1.6
-----
+ Target IP:      192.168.39.62
+ Target Hostname: www.akep.al
+ Target Port:    80
+ Start Time:    2020-02-26 15:39:24 (GMT)
-----
+ Server: Apache
+ The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options header is not present.
+ The X-XSS-Protection header is not defined. This header can hint to the user agent to protect against some forms of XSS
+ The X-Content-Type-Options header is not set. This could allow the user agent to render the content of the site in a different fashion to the MIME type
+ Root page / redirects to: https://www.akep.al/
+ /webmail/d/blank.html: ILoHaMail 0.8.10 contains an XSS vulnerability. Previous versions contain other non-descript vulnerabilities.
+ /securecontrolpanel/: Web Server Control Panel
+ /webmail/: Web based mail package installed.
+ /cgi-sys/Count.cgi: This may allow attackers to execute arbitrary commands on the server
+ OSVDB-3233: /mailman/ListInfo: Mailman was found on the server.
+ OSVDB-2117: /cpanel/: Web-based control panel
+ OSVDB-3892: /img-sys/: Default image directory should not allow directory listing.
+ ERROR: Error limit (20) reached for host, giving up. Last error: error reading HTTP response
+ Scan terminated: 10 error(s) and 10 item(s) reported on remote host
+ End Time:      2020-02-26 15:53:22 (GMT) (1838 seconds)
-----
+ 1 host(s) tested
```

Figure 3 Nikto scanning 2.

B. The Harvester

Using Harvester we collected six email addresses of Akep employees, who may also be admins of the website. An attacker can exploit this information by performing a phishing

attack to them and consequently gaining access to Akep system.

“Phishing is a type of social engineering attack often used to steal user data, including login credentials and credit card numbers. It occurs when an attacker, masquerading as a trusted entity, dupes a victim into opening an email, instant message, or text message.”

```
[*] Target: www.akep.al
[*] Searching Google.
  Searching 0 results.
  Searching 100 results.
  Searching 200 results.
  Searching 300 results.
  Searching 400 results.
  Searching 500 results.
  Searching 600 results.
  Searching 700 results.
  Searching 800 results.
  Searching 900 results.
  Searching 1000 results.

[*] No IPs found.

[*] Emails found: 6
-----
aferdita.gjongecaj@akep.al
domain@akep.al
info@akep.al
numeracioni@akep.al
piro.xhixho@akep.al
portabiliteti@akep.al

[*] Hosts found: 4
-----
22www.akep.al:
2522www.akep.al:
www.akep.al:192.185.46.64
x22www.akep.al:
```

Figure 4 Harvester for Akep employees.

C. UniScan

We can use this tool to get information about directories and backups. It performs web crawl and for example, if we need to access the admin panel, it gives us an idea of how its directories look like. The HTTP 200 OK success status response code shows that the request is successful. Code 302 shows an URL redirection and can be exploited to make a redirect attack where attacker injects code instead of redirection page. In Akep directory check UniScan finds 45 URL- s. Also, through external hosts we get information about Akep domains.

```
CODE: 200 URL: http://akep.al/tar/
CODE: 200 URL: http://akep.al/ver/
CODE: 200 URL: http://akep.al/version/

Crawling finished, found: 45 URL's

File Upload Forms:

External hosts:
http://www.webhost.al
http://www.ederhost.com
http://www.albtelecom.al
https://www.icnirp.org
http://www.albaniandomains.al
https://wordpress.org
http://www.efis.dk
http://www.iregister.al
http://www.digicom.al
http://www.host.al
```

```
-DYNAMIC TESTS

Learning New Directories: 0 New directories added.

FCKeditor tests:

Timthumb < 1.33 vulnerability:

Backup Files:
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/maps.google.com.bkp
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/bkp
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/~
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/fonts.googleapis.com.bkp
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/s.w.org.bkp
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/fonts.googleapis.com/css.bkp
CODE: 302 URL: http://akep.al/capture.bkp
```

Figure 5 UniScan tool.

D. SqlMap

Through SqlMap we get information about database type (Postgresql). Currently Akep is not vulnerable against SQL injection, although lagging has been detected which is very critical and combined with other techniques can be exploited for dumping their database.

```
[19:31:47] [WARNING] reflective value(s) found and filtering out
[19:32:18] [INFO] testing 'Boolean-based blind - Parameter replace (original value)
[19:32:18] [INFO] testing 'MySQL > 5.0 AND error-based - WHERE, HAVING, ORDER BY or GROUP BY clause (FLOOR)'
[19:32:18] [INFO] testing 'PostgreSQL AND error-based - WHERE or HAVING clause'
[19:32:18] [INFO] testing 'Microsoft SQL Server/Sybase AND error-based - WHERE or HAVING clause (IN)'
[19:32:18] [INFO] testing 'Oracle AND error-based - WHERE or HAVING clause (XMLType)'
[19:32:21] [INFO] testing 'MySQL > 5.0 error-based - Parameter replace (FLOOR)'
[19:32:21] [INFO] testing 'MySQL inline queries'
[19:32:21] [INFO] testing 'PostgreSQL inline queries'
[19:32:22] [INFO] testing 'Microsoft SQL Server/Sybase inline queries'
[19:32:22] [INFO] testing 'PostgreSQL > 8.1 stacked queries (comment)'
[19:32:22] [CRITICAL] considerable lagging has been detected in connection response(s). Please use as high value for option '--time-sec' as possible (e.g. 10 or more)
[19:32:31] [INFO] testing 'Microsoft SQL Server/Sybase stacked queries (comment)'
[19:32:40] [INFO] testing 'Oracle stacked queries (DBMS_PIPE.RECEIVE_MESSAGE - comment)'
[19:32:42] [INFO] testing 'MySQL > 5.0.12 AND time-based blind (SLEEP)'
[19:32:44] [INFO] testing 'PostgreSQL > 8.1 AND time-based blind'
[19:32:47] [INFO] testing 'Microsoft SQL Server/Sybase time-based blind (IF)'
[19:32:51] [INFO] testing 'Oracle AND time-based blind'
[19:32:51] [INFO] testing 'Generic UNION query (NULL) - 1 to 10 columns'
[19:32:51] [WARNING] GET parameter 's' does not seem to be injectable
[19:32:52] [INFO] all tested parameters do not appear to be injectable. Try to increase values for '--level/--risk' options if you wish to perform more tests. If you suspect that there is some kind of protection mechanism involved (e.g. WAF) maybe you could try to use option '--tamper' (e.g. '--tamper=space2comment') and/or switch '--random-agent', skipping to the next form
[19:33:27] [WARNING] HTTP error codes detected during run:
400 (Not Acceptable) - 45 times
[19:33:27] [INFO] you can find results of scanning in multiple targets made inside the CSV file '/home/venomorph/.sqlmap/output/results-82262809_8731pm.csv'
```

Figure 6 SqlMap for database information.

E. GolisMero

The most important part in GolisMero is scanning with Nmap through which we get information about open ports. We notice Akep has many open ports (port 21 ftp, port 53 dns, port 22 SSH which we can access remotely, port 80 http, port 587 MSA, port 110/143 POP3/IMAP).

```
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 1.00% percent done...
[-] Nmap: Completed Parallel DNS resolution of 1 host. at 19:21. 0.03s elapsed
[-] Nmap: Enitasking Connect Scan at 19:21
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 21/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 53/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] SQLScan: Launching SQLScan against! www.akep.al
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 22/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 3.14% percent done...
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 4.14% percent done...
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 587/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 1507/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 992/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 993/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 143/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 997/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nmap: Done Transfer: DNS done Transfer failed, server 'akep.al' not vulnerable
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 6.25% percent done...
[-] Nikto: Launching Nikto against! www.akep.al
[-] Nikto: - Host: 192.185.39.62
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 7.25% percent done...
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 8.25% percent done...
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 9.25% percent done...
[-] Nmap: Discovered open port 262/tcp on 192.185.39.62
[-] DNS BruteForcer: 10.00% percent done...
[-] Nikto: - Target IP: 192.185.39.62
[-] Nikto: - Target Hostname: www.akep.al
[-] Nikto: - Start Time: 2020-02-26 19:21:18 (GMT)
[-] Nikto: - Server: Apache
[-] Nmap: Discovered 22 open ports on 192.185.39.62
[-] Nikto: - Host page 2 redirects to: https://www.akep.al/
```

Figure 7 GolisMero is scanning with Nmap.

Even though Akep website is protected with ssl, we can exploit information about TLS versions and find vulnerabilities in any of them.

```
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.2 256 bits ECDHE-RSA-AES256-SHA Curve P-256 DHE 256
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.2 128 bits ECDHE-RSA-AES128-SHA Curve P-256 DHE 256
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.2 256 bits DHE-RSA-AES256-SHA DHE 2048 bits
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.2 128 bits DHE-RSA-AES128-SHA DHE 2048 bits
[*] SSLScan: Preferred TLSv1.1 256 bits ECDHE-RSA-AES256-SHA Curve P-256 DHE 256
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.1 128 bits ECDHE-RSA-AES128-SHA Curve P-256 DHE 256
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.1 256 bits DHE-RSA-AES256-SHA DHE 2048 bits
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.1 128 bits DHE-RSA-AES128-SHA DHE 2048 bits
[*] SSLScan: Preferred TLSv1.0 256 bits ECDHE-RSA-AES256-SHA Curve P-256 DHE 256
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.0 128 bits ECDHE-RSA-AES128-SHA Curve P-256 DHE 256
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.0 256 bits DHE-RSA-AES256-SHA DHE 2048 bits
[*] SSLScan: Accepted TLSv1.0 128 bits DHE-RSA-AES128-SHA DHE 2048 bits
```

Figure 8 TLS Information.

A very important information found from Golismero scan is that their certificates outdates in May 14 2020. After this date Akep website will be even more vulnerable than it is now.

```
[*] SSLScan: SSL Certificate:
[*] SSLScan: Signature Algorithm: sha256WithRSAEncryption
[*] SSLScan: RSA Key Strength: 2048
[*] SSLScan:
[*] SSLScan: Subject: akep.fj-technology.com
[*] SSLScan: AltNames: DNS:akep.al, DNS:akep.fj-technology.com, DNS:www.akep.al, DNS:www.akep.fj-technology.com
[*] SSLScan: Issuer: Let's Encrypt Authority X3
[*] SSLScan:
[*] SSLScan: Not valid before: Feb 14 10:27:46 2020 GMT
[*] SSLScan: Not valid after: May 14 10:27:46 2020 GMT
[*] SSLScan: SSLScan scan finished in 23.9908388983 seconds for target: ww.akep.al
[*] SSLScan: 'NoneType' object has no attribute 'group'
[*] SSLScan: Found 1 SSL vulnerabilities.
[*] DNS Bruteforcer: 96.48% percent done...
[*] DNS Bruteforcer: 97.53% percent done...
[*] DNS Bruteforcer: 98.58% percent done...
[*] DNS Bruteforcer: 99.63% percent done...
[*] DNS Bruteforcer: Found 5 subdomains for root domain: akep.al
[*] Bruteforce predictables discovery: Loaded 147 URLs to test.
```

Figure 9 SSL web certificate.

With addresses collected from Harvester we can try to make a Brute Force attack for finding password. If complexity of password is high, we can establish a Man in the Middle attack to sniff passwords and then decrypt them.

Figure 10 Password collection.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

- Penetration testing is a comprehensive method that identify the vulnerabilities in a system.
- In this performed test, we used an Albanian website by utilizing automated tools. Based on all obtained results, we came to the conclusions that this web page has a medium-to -high level of security so it is vulnerable to a security risk that could allow hackers attack its software and infrastructure. It's necessary to do some improvements on the system and the code should be better constructed.
- In the future, we are going to perform other pen tests on Albanian websites.
- To our opinion, it is better for each company to test the security of their software using penetration test.

REFERENCES

[1] <http://nmap.org>
 [2] <https://searchsoftwarequality.techtarget.com>
 [3] David Kennedy,Jim O’Gorman, Devon Kearns, Metasploit --The Penetration Tester’s Guide.
 [4] Gorgia Weidman, Penetration testing a Hands-on introduction to Hacking, San Francisco.
 [5] Adison Wesley Professional, “Software Security- Building Security In” McGraw, G.(2006).
 [6] <https://www.exploit-db.com>.
 [7] <https://www.rapid7.com>.